

EFFECT OF COBRA (*NAJA NAJA*) VENOM AND ITS CONSTITUENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF ACETYLCHOLINE BY THE BRAIN CELLS OF THE RATS AND PIGEONS

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Effect of cobra venom and some of its active principles on the synthesis of acetylcholine by the brain cells of rats and pigeons, suspended in oxygenated phosphate-Locke-glucose medium has been studied. Results indicate that cobra venom inhibits the synthesis of acetylcholine.

It has now been well established by the researches of Quastel and co-workers (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, **30**, 1668; 1938, **32**, 243; 1939, **33**, 822) and Stedman and Stedman (*ibid.*, 1937, **31**, 817) that acetylcholine is synthesised by the brain cells of animals. Quastel and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) report that the substance is formed partly in a free state and partly in a complex form and that the synthesis occurs best in the presence of glucose and oxygen. Stedman and Stedman (*loc. cit.*), however, maintain that glucose has no appreciable influence on this synthetic process. The importance of acetylcholine in the transmission of nerve impulse makes it desirable to study the effect of cobra venom on its synthesis by animal tissues. Gautrelet and Corteggiani (*Compt. rend. Soc. biol.*, 1938, **207**, 456) state that cobra venom can bring about a rapid decomposition of the acetylcholine complex with the liberation of free acetylcholine. In this paper the results of investigation on the effect of cobra venom and some of its active principles on the synthesis of acetylcholine by the brain cells of the rats and pigeons have been recorded.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Immediately after the animal was killed its brain was removed and minced and, divided into a number of approximately equal parts. Weighed quantities of the minced brain were put into a number of conical flasks of the Warburg respiratory apparatus and to each of them were added 3.0 c.c. of phosphate-Locke solution containing 1 in 7000 eserine sulphate. The composition of the phosphate-Locke solution used was:—NaCl, 0.13M; KCl, 0.002M; CaCl₂, 0.001M; phosphate buffer p_n 7.4, 0.03 M. The flasks were fitted to the manometers, filled with oxygen and placed in a bath at 37°. The experiment lasted for 2 to 3 hours and during this period the flasks were continually shaken. When the experiment was completed the p_n of the solution in the flask was brought to 3.0 for the decomposition of the acetylcholine complex as suggested by Quastel and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) and after 30 minutes the content of the flask was neutralised and the acetylcholine estimated by measuring the contraction of the dorsal muscle of the leech. The muscle isolated from the leech was immersed in 7.0 c.c. of a saline solution of the following composition:—NaCl, 0.71%; KCl, 0.032%; CaCl₂, 0.0118%; NaHCO₃, 0.012%; glucose, 0.77%.

Oxygen was bubbled through the solution at a steady rate. The muscle with one end attached to a hook and the other to a lever by means of a silk thread, was allowed to stand in a slightly stretched condition in the oxygenated saline medium for about an hour. 0.01 Mg. of eserine sulphate was then added to the solution and after about 15 minutes this eserimised solution was removed. The muscle was washed once with the saline medium and again allowed to stand immersed in 7.0 c.c. of the oxygenated saline solution for nearly two hours to attain

a steady condition. The solution (0.3 c.c.), the acetylcholine content of which was to be estimated, was added and the contraction was recorded on a slowly revolving smoked drum by the lever attached to the muscle. The muscle was washed with the saline medium after each contraction and allowed to regain its original length before the next measurement was started. Contractions produced by known quantities of acetylcholine chloride were also measured and from a comparison of these data with those of the unknown, the acetylcholine content of the latter was calculated.

Effect of Cobra Venom

The venom used in the following experiments was extracted from the monocellate variety of cobra and dried as soon as possible after extraction in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride. The minimum lethal dose of the dry venom for a pigeon (390 g. to 320 g.) was 0.1 mg. The results are recorded in Table I. The estimated value of acetylcholine chloride is expressed in γ per gram of wet tissue and the data under the condition (E) give the amount of total acetylcholine present in the tissue at the commencement of the experiment. It has been observed by us that the contraction of the dorsal muscle of the leech by acetylcholine is in no way affected by the presence of cobra venom in the doses used.

From a comparison of the data under the conditions indicated in (A), (B), (C) and (D) it will be noticed that glucose strongly favours the synthesis and that cobra venom in the doses of 2 to 4 m.l.d. markedly inhibits the formation of acetylcholine by the brain tissues of rats and pigeons. The extent of inhibition is greater, the higher the dose of venom used.

TABLE I

The brain tissue was minced at about 0°, thoroughly mixed and divided into a number of approximately equal parts.

Expt.	Species of brain.	Treatment.	Period of incubation.	Total acetylcholine chloride.
1.	Pigeon	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution	2 hrs.	2.90 γ /g.
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02 M) added to the solution	2	8.75
		(C) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the solution	2	4.25
		(D) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.4 mg. added to the solution	2	3.40
		(E) Same as in (A)	0	1.80
2.	Pigeon	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution	2	2.60
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the solution	2	9.60
		(C) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the solution	2	5.76
		(D) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.4 mg. added to the solution	2	4.00
		(E) Same as in (A)	0	1.86
3.	Pigeon	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine solution	2	2.44
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the solution	2	8.50
		(C) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the solution	2	4.86
		(D) Same as in (A)	0	1.50
4.	Rat	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine solution	2	2.70
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the solution	2	10.80
		(C) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the solution	2	5.64*

Effect of Neurotoxin (R)

A neurotoxin was isolated from cobra venom by Ghosh and De (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1941, 29, 367). This neurotoxin was weight for weight 16 times more active than the original venom and was found to be responsible for the failure of the respiratory movement. It has therefore been denoted as 'neurotoxin (R)'; the suffix (R) indicating that it affects the respiratory system. The minimum lethal dose for pigeons of this toxin was 0.0065 mg. The results are recorded in Table II. It will be noticed from the data that this neurotoxin in doses of 2 to 3 m. l. d. has very little effect on the synthesis of acetylcholine by the brain tissues of rats and pigeons.

TABLE II

The brain was minced at about 0°, thoroughly mixed and divided into a number of approximately equal parts.

Expt.	Species of brain.	Treatment.	Period of incubation.	Total acetylcholine chloride.
1.	Pigeon	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution	0 hrs.	1.557 g.
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the solution	2	8.42
		(C) Same as in (B) but neurotoxin (R) 0.013 mg. added to the system	2	7.90
2.	Pigeon	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution	0	1.04
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the solution	2	6.40
		(C) Same as in (B) but neurotoxin (R) 0.02 mg. added to the system	2	6.40
3.	Pigeon	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution	0	2.00
		(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the solution	2	7.40
		(C) Same as in (B) but neurotoxin (R) 0.013 mg. added to the system	2	6.90
4.	Rat	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine solution	2	8.80
		(B) Same as in (A) but neurotoxin (R) 0.013 mg. added to the system	2	7.95

Effect of the Inhibitor of Glycolysis and Respiration

It has been observed by us that cobra venom contains an active principle which inhibits respiration and the formation of lactic acid from glucose by the brain cells of pigeons. We have succeeded in partially separating the active principle from the crude venom. Assuming that cobra venom contains this inhibitor and the neurotoxin in the proportion of 100:100 the sample which we have isolated contains the two active principles in the proportion of 100:13. This sample is therefore considerably richer in the inhibitor of glycolysis and

respiration than the original venom. The results obtained by using this fraction are recorded in Table III. It will be noticed that this fraction containing the inhibitor of glycolysis and respiration is much more active than cobra venom in suppressing the synthesis of acetylcholine by the brain tissues of rats and pigeons.

TABLE III

The brain tissue was minced at about 0°, thoroughly mixed and divided into a number of approximately equal parts.

Expt.	Treatment.	Period of incubation	Total acetylcholine chloride
1.	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution	0 hrs.	1.50 γ /g.
	(B) Same as in (A) but glucose (0.02M) added to the system	2	8.45
	(C) Same as in (B) but inhibitor of respiration and glycolysis 0.06 mg. added to the system	2	5.50
	(D) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the system	2	4.90
2.	(A) One part brain, 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) solution and glucose (0.02M)	2	9.20
	(B) Same as in (A) but inhibitor of respiration and glycolysis 0.06 mg. added to the system	2	5.70
	(C) Same as in (A) but the inhibitor 0.12 mg. added to the system	2	4.75
	(D) Same as in (B) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the system	2	4.60
3.	(A) One part brain 3.0 c.c. phosphate-Locke eserine (1:7000) and glucose (0.02M).	2	8.88
	(B) Same as in (A) but the inhibitor 0.06 mg. added to the system	2	5.0
	(C) Same as in (A) but the inhibitor 0.12 mg. added to the system	2	4.0
	(D) Same as in (A) but cobra venom 0.2 mg. added to the system	2	4.7

CONCLUSION

The effect of cobra venom and some of the active principles isolated from it, on the synthesis of acetylcholine by the brain cells of rats and pigeons suspended in oxygenated phosphate-Locke-glucose medium has been investigated. It has been found that cobra venom inhibits the synthesis of acetylcholine and that this inhibition is very probably brought about by the inhibitor of respiration and glycolysis contained in the venom. The neurotoxin (R) which may be called the respiratory toxin, as it affects the respiratory system, has very little influence on the synthesis of the choline ester by the brain cells of rats and pigeons. It remains yet to be determined whether the observed inhibition of respiration and glycolysis is caused by one or more than one active principle.